

USING VISUAL SUPPORTS (IMAGES, VIDEOS) TO ENHANCE LISTENING COMPEHENTION

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Abstract: Listening is a fundamental ability to train English. The purpose of this article is to describe the use of audiovisual media in improving students listening skills. The primary purpose of this research is to know the application of sound learning to sound development in improving listening and understanding the ability to listen to English students after learning how to use visual media. This review is quantitative. About data analysis, percentage, and point t-test, the sample was used. The results show that students of English students a significant increase in understanding after learning with videos and students the positive attitude for using videos in listening to listening skills.

Keywords: audio visual media, listening skill, authentic materials, listening comprehension, video materials.

INTRODUCTION

English is considered as one of the important parts to be learned by students in Indonesia. It is taught from kindergarten school, elementary school, junior high school, senior high school, and university level. The English teaching and learning process are aimed at a highly important-role to develop the students' competence in English both spoken and written especially in junior high school. By learning English, students can develop the understanding of the relationship between language and culture, gain a chance to better career in modern society's lives, and expanding the skills of the language: listening, speaking, reading, and writing.

Nevertheless, listening is considered one of the important skills for Junior High School students in foreign language learning because the key to learning a language is to receive language by hearing. According to Sarita (2019: 57), "In English learning and teaching, listening is a skill that is learnt by learners equally with another skill. Since one of the purposes of language is to communicate, listening takes an important role in the language. It means listening is one of the English skills which must be mastered by English learners. On other hand, mastering listening skill is not easy for some students. Most students have difficulties in learning listening skill.

English teachers have an important role to support and improve their students in practicing listening skills in the classroom. Teachers need to be creative to transform a classroom activities to teach listening. They should consider the interests of students who determine whether the activities are appropriate or not.

The second problem was related to the teacher. The teacher had difficulties finding the listening materials so the learning and teaching process is done by simply reading the text on the book then the students are asked to listen to it only and sometimes English native speaker's recording materials were too difficult for the students. The last problem was related to the media. The lack of innovation in the use of media so that learning listening skills make the students easily saturated and bored.

LITERATUREREVIEW

Learning a foreign language as a second language is a dynamic process in which several factors affect learners' linguistic development. The most widely used language for those who speak a foreign language as a second language is English in Vietnam. It is very difficult to acquire a foreign language, but there are ways to help second language learners learn the new language more easily with each skill. I want to speak on how to improve communication skills in this study. One of the problematic skills for learners, especially young kids, is internal listening. Therefore to help kids learn this skill well through media, we need very appropriate learning methods. Practical listening abilities help you understand what the speaker needs to say and edit the pronunciation and standardize it.

The Use of Authentic Materials

The use of authentic materials in the classroom has been supported by many researchers. One of the first researchers to propose this notion was Krashen in 1982 who pointed out that authentic learning experiences provide learners an opportunity to acquire the target language. Clarke has also stated that the language of the real world is what learners need to be exposed to because that language is uncompromising towards the learner and reflects real world goals and situations. Therefore, authentic materials need to be presented to the language learners because they reflect how the language is used in authentic communication. The application of authentic materials can also enhance the students' familiarity with forms of the language and it's use in communications. As a student I should mention that finding authentic audio materials is complex since we should pay attention to the meaning and the condition. When it comes to songs, using them for young learners makes the process more productive because they learn And enjoy at the same time. Professionals in favor of using authentic materials assert that exposure to authentic materials should be introduced to learners at the earliest stages of language learning [3;462] have claimed that early exposure to authentic texts will aid students to develop useful strategies for more complex tasks later on. The findings of the above-mentioned studies have indicated that authentic materials can be useful in many ways. Such materials introduce students to how language is used in the real world and improve their overall language proficiency as well as improving reading and listening skills, communicative competence, and lexical and stylistic knowledge.

The advantages of using videos

Using videos has been closely associated with developing listening skills. Videos as learning materials have received a great deal of attention from educators and their effects have been positively reported in various areas. Extensive research has been conducted into the possible effects of using videos to enhance language learning: to provide a rich context for authentic discourse, to improve listening comprehension, to enhance learners' achievements

and motivation, and to acquire a better understand of non-verbal expressions. There are many advantages of using video materials:

Firstly, there is a visual aspect, students can listen the target language and watch real movements as videos are dynamic, this helps them to remember better because visual memory is much stronger in many students and visualization can help to lessen misunderstanding for instance a child while watching video related to body parts may not to understand which part is that but after watching it they may realize it in an easy way.

Secondly, most videos have subtitles, these help bridge between reading and listening .teachers might cover them or simply not show them , it can only be used as helping aid.

One of another major advantages of using video is that it can provide samples of real-life situations. Lonergan pointed out that video is able to present “complete communicative situations.

Next, videos can be controlled. The pause button allows teacher to divide the long material into small short pieces. The rewind button comes to help when learners are confused, we can even avoid the long watch, with double pushing we can find the required moment.

CONCLUSION

I can say that the use of audio and video materials to develop listening comprehension is effective and enhances student’s listening comprehension ability due to the combination of visual images and sound which stimulate student’s perceptions. In addition, we should acknowledge the importance of the tone and speed of speech which are spontaneous, similar to that in daily-life situations.

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